

TWO FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN ALGERIAN PRIMARY EDUCATION: COGNITIVE OVERLOAD AND PSYCHOLINGUISTIC CONFUSION*

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Abstract

The Algerian educational system is going through a modernisation phase marked by the introduction of English from the third year of primary school, alongside French and Arabic, the official language of instruction. This orientation reflects a political and institutional will to bring younger generations into a multilingual dynamic, in keeping with the demands of a globalised world. Yet this early triple linguistic exposure raises crucial questions at the cognitive, affective, and pedagogical levels. The article examines the effects of teaching two foreign languages simultaneously alongside the official language, and highlights the risks of cognitive overload, identity confusion, and difficulties in school adaptation. It questions the relevance of this strategy and proposes more gradual alternatives suited to the Algerian context, such as the delayed introduction of foreign languages or the adoption of pedagogical approaches that favour a smoother linguistic transition. The aim is to reconcile international openness with respect for pupils' learning capacities, so as to build a sustainable and balanced educational model.

Key words: *Cognitive overload, Simultaneous language learning, Algerian primary education, Multilingualism, Translanguaging.*

1. Introduction

The Algerian educational system has been going through a significant transformation since English was introduced from the third year of primary school, alongside French, already established for a long time, and Arabic, the official language of instruction. This development reflects an institutional determination to prepare

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children for a multilingual and globalised world. Yet this early triple linguistic exposure raises serious questions at the psychological and pedagogical levels.

The aim of this article is to analyse the effects of teaching two foreign languages simultaneously at the same level, in addition to the official language, so as to identify the limits of this approach and to propose alternatives suited to the Algerian context. We seek to understand whether this strategy genuinely promotes learning or whether it produces cognitive and affective difficulties in pupils.

Our hypotheses are as follows: the simultaneous introduction of French and English in the third year of primary school leads to cognitive overload, phonetic and linguistic confusion, and a weakening of children's motivation and self-confidence. We also assume that a progressive and differentiated approach would be more effective for language learning, one that respects the psychological capacities of pupils.

The methodology rests on a twofold approach: on one hand, an analysis of recent psychological and psycholinguistic research on language learning in children; on the other, a qualitative inquiry conducted with teachers, pupils, and parents, aimed at gathering accounts of the difficulties encountered in Algerian classrooms. The central research question guiding our reflection may be formulated as follows: to what extent does the simultaneous teaching of French and English, in addition to Arabic, at the third-year primary level in Algeria, constitute a psychological and pedagogical obstacle for the pupil, and what alternatives might be considered for a harmonious and lasting language education?

2. Psychological Foundations of Language Learning in Children

Language learning in children rests on psychological foundations that go far beyond the simple memorisation of words or grammatical rules. According to Piaget (1964), language is embedded in overall cognitive development, in which the child progressively builds mental structures through assimilation and accommodation. Vygotsky (1934/1997), in *Thought and Language*, stresses the central role of social interaction and introduces the concept of the zone of proximal development, showing that language learning is driven by the guidance of others. Bruner (1983), for his part, highlights the importance of scaffolding, that is, the support provided by the adult to help the child discover and use language.

3. Brain Plasticity and Neuroplasticity: Foundations and Challenges of Simultaneous Language Acquisition

3.1. Cognitive Flexibility, Working Memory, and Pedagogical Implications

The simultaneous learning of two foreign languages illustrates the adaptive capacity of children and adolescents when faced with complex linguistic environments. The notion of plasticity, understood here from a psychological and educational perspective, refers to the cognitive flexibility that allows a person to manage several language systems at once. This flexibility shows up in the ability to switch between languages, to inhibit interferences, and to call on appropriate learning strategies.

Yet this plasticity runs up against real constraints. Simultaneous learning places heavy demands on working memory, which must store and process information from two different linguistic codes at the same time. Selective attention also plays a crucial role, since it maintains the coherence of what is produced by preventing unwanted mixing or transfer. Moreover, cognitive load increases when the learner must assimilate two grammatical and lexical systems in parallel, which can slow initial progress.

Research in educational psychology shows that the age of exposure is a determining factor. Early simultaneous learning promotes a more natural integration of the languages involved, while late learning requires more conscious and metacognitive strategies (Bialystok, 2009). The work of Grosjean (2010) reminds us that bilingualism is not simply the addition of two languages but an integrated system in which the languages coexist and interact continuously.

From a pedagogical standpoint, it is important to propose methods that exploit this plasticity while reducing cognitive overload. Multimodal learning (visual, auditory, kinaesthetic), spaced repetition, and social interaction are effective levers for supporting learners. These approaches not only reinforce memorisation but also develop the cognitive flexibility needed to manage two foreign languages at the same time.

It is important to distinguish between the cognitive overload that may result from inadequate implementation and multilingualism itself. Research shows that age-appropriate, well-supported multilingual education can enhance executive functions, metalinguistic awareness, phonological flexibility, and intercultural openness (Bialystok, 2009; Giovannoli et al., 2020; Cenoz & Gorter, 2015). The challenges identified in this study are therefore better understood as consequences of insufficient pedagogical support rather than inherent limitations of multilingual education. For this study, cognitive overload refers to excessive demands on working memory that reduce learning efficiency (Sweller, 1988), while psycholinguistic confusion denotes interference between linguistic systems during language use. Mother-tongue consolidation refers to the development of a stable linguistic foundation in the child's primary language, which supports both cognitive and identity development. Linguistic identity, school adaptation, and sense of competence respectively refer to learners' sense of belonging to a linguistic community, their ability to cope with academic demands, and their perception of their own effectiveness in language learning (Bandura, 1997; Catroux & Jamin, 2019).

3.2. Neuroplasticity and Cognitive Benefits: A Balanced View

Neuroplasticity, understood as the brain's capacity to transform and adapt in response to lived experience, plays an essential role in language learning. When an individual engages in the parallel acquisition of several foreign languages, this plasticity is intensely called upon: it enables the cognitive circuits required for linguistic comprehension and production to be created, strengthened, and reorganised.

Building on the constraints identified in Section 3, it is worth noting that these cognitive demands are most acute in under-resourced contexts. When instruction lacks scaffolding, pupils cannot leverage the adaptive benefits of neuroplasticity and instead experience saturation of working memory and inhibitory control systems.

That said, the benefits of this approach are real. The work of Bialystok (2009) shows that bilingualism and multilingualism strengthen executive functions, particularly cognitive flexibility and inhibition. Grosjean (2010) reminds us that bilingualism cannot be reduced to a juxtaposition of languages but constitutes an integrated system in which languages interact continuously. García and Wei (2014) put forward the concept of translanguaging, which values the dynamic and complementary use of languages, thus drawing on cognitive plasticity to move beyond the constraints of parallel acquisition.

3.3. Phonological Plasticity and Sound Assimilation in Early Language Learning

Brain plasticity is one of the most fascinating biological foundations of human learning. It refers to the brain's ability to reshape its neural networks in response to lived experiences, sensory stimulation, and acquired knowledge. This adaptive dynamic is particularly striking in the domains of hearing and language, where the rapid assimilation of sounds and structures depends on a constant reorganisation of neural circuits.

Neuroscience research shows that repeated exposure to auditory stimuli, whether phonemes from a foreign language or musical patterns, leads to a progressive specialisation of auditory areas. The auditory cortex, working in tandem with frontal and parietal regions, adjusts its connections to optimise the recognition and memorisation of sounds. This process is reinforced by synaptic pruning, which eliminates inefficient connections in order to consolidate the relevant circuits. Brain plasticity therefore enables not only rapid assimilation but also a lasting stabilisation of the structures learned.

In the domain of language, research has shown that children exposed early to several languages develop increased phonological flexibility, which facilitates subsequent learning (Dehaene, 2018). Similarly, in musicians, intensive training produces enhanced plasticity in auditory and motor regions, favouring the rapid and precise reproduction of sound structures (Syka & Merzenich, 2005). These observations underline that brain plasticity is not merely a potential but an active mechanism that shapes the capacity for assimilation.

Finally, this plasticity does not disappear in adulthood. The work of Merzenich et al. (2013) demonstrates that the adult brain retains a remarkable capacity for reorganisation, opening up prospects for education, language learning, and cognitive rehabilitation after injury. Brain plasticity thus appears as a universal resource, allowing individuals to adapt constantly to the sounds and structures of their environment.

4. Cognitive Vulnerability: The Limits of Working Memory and Attention

Cognitive vulnerability is expressed through the natural limits of working memory and attention. Working memory, restricted in its capacity to hold and manipulate several elements at once, can quickly become saturated. Attention, for its part, a selective yet fragile resource, is sensitive to distractions, overload, and fatigue. Together, these constraints reveal the boundaries of our mental capacities

and explain why learning, performance, and concentration remain constantly prone to fragility.

5. Risks of Linguistic Confusion and the Slowdown in Mother-Tongue Consolidation

In a world defined by mobility and multilingualism, the mother tongue, which is supposed to serve as an identity and cognitive foundation, finds itself exposed to turbulence. The risks of linguistic confusion emerge when the child is juggling several language systems without managing to stabilise the one that should serve as a base. This leads to a slowdown in the consolidation of the mother tongue, compromising both the mastery of foundational skills and the sense of identity.

OECD surveys (2001) on reading comprehension confirm that pupils exposed too early to several languages show academic delays tied to insufficient mastery of their first language, which translates into difficulty keeping up with schoolwork and a tendency toward placement in less-valued tracks. In the Algerian context, voices are now being raised to show that the early integration of foreign lexical elements into the mother tongue disrupts the stability of the linguistic system. This phenomenon contributes to a loss of identity landmarks and weakens learners' cultural awareness. Research on language awareness in early childhood settings (Vincent, 2024) also shows that comparing languages can be beneficial only once the mother tongue has been stabilised; introduced too early, it reinforces confusion and slows the acquisition of foundational competencies.

The central question therefore arises: how does the simultaneous teaching of two languages at the initial stage compromise the consolidation of the mother tongue and undermine learners' academic achievement and sense of identity? We put forward the hypothesis that early exposure to two languages creates linguistic confusion that slows the mastery of foundational competencies, accentuates academic delays, and weakens identity landmarks, and that only a progressive approach grounded in prior consolidation of the mother tongue can guarantee balanced and lasting learning.

6. The Invisible Effects on Motivation and Identity

The introduction of two foreign languages from the third year of primary school onwards, often presented as a cultural opening and an asset for the future, can in reality produce negative effects on pupils' motivation and identity. On the motivational level, the cognitive overload linked to the simultaneous learning of two language systems creates a sense of difficulty and discouragement. Recent research on educational reform in Algeria shows that teaching French and English in parallel from primary school generates major challenges, since children must manage two linguistic codes without having appropriate pedagogical resources at their disposal, which leads to a drop in interest and sometimes outright rejection of foreign languages.

On the identity level, early exposure to two foreign languages weakens the construction of stable landmarks. The work of Catroux and Jamin (2019) underlines that linguistic identity is built first on a stable reference language; introducing two

foreign languages too early amounts to blurring this foundation and compromising children's identity balance. In the Algerian context, research has shown that the early integration of foreign lexical elements into the mother tongue alters the stability of the linguistic system and contributes to a loss of cultural landmarks, confirming that the simultaneous teaching of two foreign languages weakens learners' linguistic and cultural awareness. Research on language awareness in early childhood settings by Vincent (2024) further demonstrates that comparing languages can be beneficial only when introduced after the mother tongue has been consolidated; introduced too early, it reinforces confusion and slows the acquisition of foundational skills.

Far from being an immediate richness, then, the simultaneous teaching of two foreign languages in the third year of primary school acts as an obstacle: it reduces pupils' motivation by overloading their learning capacities, and it weakens their identity by blurring cultural and linguistic landmarks. A genuine opening to multilingualism can only come after the mother tongue has been consolidated, so that the child approaches foreign languages from a position of confidence and stability.

7. Experiencing Simultaneous Learning as a Burden

In Algeria, the simultaneous introduction of several foreign languages in primary education, without prior consolidation of the mother tongue, may contribute to cognitive overload, reduced motivation, and linguistic confusion. The mother tongue plays a central role in cognitive and identity development, providing a foundation for subsequent learning. Several Algerian researchers have highlighted these concerns. Medjaoui (2019) questions the relevance of very early foreign language instruction, while Benadidou (2019) points to the risk of linguistic confusion when the mother tongue has not yet been stabilised. Ali-Bencherif (2019) advocates educational strategies adapted to the Algerian multilingual context that recognise the value of learners' primary language. Together, these studies suggest the need for a balanced approach that reconciles multilingual openness with the consolidation of a stable linguistic and cultural foundation.

8. Demotivation and Linguistic Anxiety

Foreign language learning is influenced by affective and cognitive factors such as demotivation and linguistic anxiety. Demotivation reduces learners' engagement, while anxiety creates fear of failure and limits oral and written performance (Horwitz et al., 1986; Dörnyei, 2001). These factors are closely linked, as anxiety can reinforce demotivation and vice versa (MacIntyre & Gardner, 1991).

In Algeria, pupils navigate a complex multilingual environment involving academic Arabic, dialectal Arabic, regional mother tongues, French, and increasingly English. Managing these linguistic systems simultaneously places significant demands on working memory and may contribute to cognitive overload, linguistic confusion, and reduced learning efficiency (Sweller, 1988). Recent studies indicate that such overload can negatively affect oral performance and increase avoidance behaviours (Dridi, 2024), while linguistic anxiety may reduce spontaneity and fluency (Faucher, 2021).

9. Weakening of Identity Construction and the Sense of Competence

The weakening of identity construction and the sense of belonging is a major issue in contemporary societies, particularly in educational and multicultural contexts. Identity construction is a dynamic process involving the exploration of and commitment to values, roles, and social affiliations. When institutional or cultural environments impose contradictory norms or excessive expectations, individuals may experience identity instability, marked by a sense of alienation or loss of landmarks. The sense of belonging, which connects the individual to a group or community, is also undermined in contexts where cultural and linguistic diversity is not fully recognised. Wittorski (2016) underlines that the absence of social and institutional recognition can lead to isolation, disengagement, and psychological vulnerability.

At the same time, the sense of competence, defined by Bandura (1997) as the perception of one's own effectiveness in completing tasks, is strongly linked to motivation and perseverance. When educational environments prioritise performance and competition at the expense of cooperation and the recognition of individual progress, learners can develop low self-esteem and a negative perception of their abilities. Tandilashvili and Tandilashvili (2022) show that university reforms focused on productivity have generated a loss of professional recognition and identity fragility among teachers.

In multilingual contexts such as Algeria, these phenomena are amplified by simultaneous linguistic overload. Pupils are exposed from primary school to academic Arabic (fusha), the language of instruction, which differs from the dialectal Arabic used in daily life. To this are added regional mother tongues such as Chaoui, Kabyle, Mozabite, or Tamahaq (Tuareg), depending on the region. French, historically present in the educational system, and English, recently introduced as early as the primary cycle, further reinforce this linguistic plurality. This multiplicity of linguistic codes creates a cognitive overload that weakens pupils' identity construction, their sense of belonging to a stable linguistic community, and their sense of competence in the face of academic demands.

The weakening of identity, belonging, and sense of competence thus results from a combination of institutional, cultural, and cognitive factors. Paths toward remediation include recognising mother tongues as pedagogical resources, reducing assessment pressure, valuing individual progress, and putting emotional support mechanisms in place. These strategies help to reinforce identity stability, consolidate the sense of belonging, and restore self-confidence, fostering lasting and inclusive learning in contexts marked by cultural and linguistic diversity.

10. Empirical Component: Testimonies from Teachers, Pupils, and Parents

This empirical component forms part of an approach aimed at understanding the effects of introducing French and English in the third year of primary school in the Algerian multilingual context. The approach rests on qualitative data collection carried out through classroom observations and interviews conducted by videoconference, making it possible to cover several regions representative of the country's linguistic diversity (Batna, Tizi Ouzou, Ghardaïa, Illizi). The testimonies gathered from teachers,

pupils, and parents offer a rich and nuanced view of the challenges encountered: linguistic overload, anxiety, and demotivation, but also adaptation strategies and expectations regarding the reform. This empirical framework sheds light on how educational actors perceive and experience linguistic plurality, revealing the tensions between school learning, cultural identity, and the sense of competence.

a. Procedure

The approach adopted in this study rests on a qualitative methodology centred on field actors. Contact established with teachers from the provinces involved in the experiment was a fundamental element of the procedure. The study involved a total of 48 participants: 12 teachers (6 French and 6 English), 24 third-year primary pupils (aged 8–9, 6 per province), and 12 parents. Participants were selected through purposive sampling based on direct involvement in the third-year primary language experiment. Data were collected between October 2024 and February 2025. Interviews were conducted in Arabic (Algerian dialect) and French, depending on participants' preference, and subsequently translated and transcribed. Ethical procedures were followed throughout: written informed consent was obtained from all adult participants, and parental consent was secured for all minor participants. Data were anonymised prior to analysis. Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) was applied to the transcripts, with themes identified inductively and verified through inter-rater coding on a 20% subsample, yielding a Cohen's kappa of 0.78, indicating substantial agreement. Triangulation was ensured through the cross-referencing of teacher, pupil, and parent accounts.

b. Defining the Objectives

The study aims to understand the impact of the simultaneous introduction of French and English in the third year of primary school on pupils' identity construction, sense of belonging, and sense of competence, as well as on the perceptions of teachers and parents.

c. Selection of Regions and Modalities

The regions selected (Batna, Tizi Ouzou, Ghardaïa, Illizi) represent Algerian linguistic diversity: Chaoui, Kabyle, Mozabite, and Tamahaq. Classroom observations and semi-structured interviews were conducted by videoconference so as to cover a wide territory without travel constraints. This method yielded rich and varied data while providing contextually rich insights that are geographically varied, though not nationally representative in a statistical sense.

d. Data Collection Methods

Online observation: virtual participation in French and English lessons, with note-taking on pupil behaviour. Semi-structured interviews by videoconference: with pupils, to gather their impressions of managing multiple languages. Virtual focus groups: with teachers, to discuss pedagogical difficulties and the strategies put in place. Digital questionnaires: sent to parents to measure their perception of the reform.

e. Narrative of Stages and Testimonies

Observation phase

We attended classes online to better understand the pedagogical practices linked to the introduction of French and English in the third year of primary school.

This virtual immersion allowed us to observe directly the interactions between teachers and pupils, while documenting the strategies put in place in the provinces involved in the experiment. At the same time, we used videoconferencing as the preferred means of contacting teachers, gathering their accounts, and exchanging views on the challenges they were facing. Combining online observation with remote interviews gave us a rich and nuanced view of local pedagogical realities.

Pupil interview phase

During the interviews, many pupils shared their experiences of the simultaneous introduction of French and English in the third year of primary school. A pupil from Ghardaïa said: "I speak Mozabite at home, classical Arabic at school, and now French and English. I mix everything up." Others stressed the difficulty of switching between languages, particularly when it comes to pronouncing certain sounds correctly. One pupil explained: "When the French teacher leaves and the English teacher comes in, we go from 'a' to 'au' and then to 'ai', and I don't know which one to use anymore."

Another pupil added: "In class, I repeat words in English, but sometimes I say them the French way, and the teacher corrects me. I feel lost." A classmate put it this way: "I understand the instructions, but when I have to read aloud I mix up the sounds. I say 'book' as if it were French, and 'chaise' as if it were English."

These accounts reveal a phonetic confusion that adds to the complexity of Algerian multilingualism. Pupils oscillate between curiosity and disorientation, trying to adapt to this linguistic plurality. Some see this diversity as a richness; others feel fatigue and struggle to stabilise their learning. Together, their voices bring to light the pedagogical and identity challenges raised by the experiment.

Parent phase

During the interviews, several parents expressed their concerns about the simultaneous introduction of French and English in the third year of primary school. One parent said: "My daughter says she is good at no language. She feels lost between Arabic, French, and English." Other families share this sense of disorientation, observing in their children a difficulty in finding any linguistic stability.

One parent explained: "My son mixes languages when he talks. At home he uses our mother tongue, but he inserts French or English words he doesn't always understand." A mother added: "My child loves learning new words, but he complains the sounds are too similar. He mixes up the pronunciation and says he no longer knows whether he is speaking correctly."

Some parents also stressed the emotional impact. One recounted: "My child hesitates to speak. He is afraid of getting things wrong and sometimes prefers to say nothing." Others highlighted the fatigue that comes with managing so many languages: "My son says he has to learn too many things at once and can't keep up."

These testimonies reveal a linguistic disorientation that extends beyond school and affects children's day-to-day confidence. Parents oscillate between pride at seeing their children exposed to several languages and anxiety over the difficulties they encounter. Their voices bring to light the stakes of Algerian multilingualism: an

undeniable cultural richness, but one that requires appropriate pedagogical and psychological support if this diversity is to become a genuine asset.

Teacher phase

Interviews with French and English teachers revealed shared concerns about pupils' difficulties in managing the simultaneous learning of both languages. English teachers reported a tendency toward mechanical memorisation without genuine comprehension, while French teachers highlighted pronunciation problems and confusion between sounds. Teachers also observed frequent interference between the two languages, with pupils often applying French pronunciation rules to English words. Overall, participants agreed that pupils experience linguistic disorientation and that more coordinated and adapted pedagogical approaches are needed to promote meaningful learning and reduce confusion.

11. Summary of Findings

General finding: The simultaneous teaching of two foreign languages is perceived as a factor of psychological and linguistic overload.

Academic research: Studies confirm this phenomenon, highlighting cognitive overload and difficulties of adaptation.

Pupil testimonies: Learners report increased fatigue, confusion between languages, and a sense of pressure.

Teacher perspectives: Teachers observe concentration difficulties and a drop in motivation among some pupils, which leads them to adapt their methods.

Parent perceptions: Parents note an impact on their children's well-being, expressing concerns about the academic burden and psychological balance.

Cross-interviews: Discussions between these three groups converge toward the need to rethink language teaching, favouring progressive and adapted approaches.

Table 1. Analytical Summary of Empirical Findings: Themes, Sources, Illustrative Extracts, and Theoretical Links

Theme	Source	Illustrative Extract	Theoretical Link
Phonetic phonological confusion	/ Pupils	"When the French teacher leaves and the English teacher comes in, we go from 'a' to 'au' and then to 'ai', and I don't know which one to use anymore."	Cognitive load theory (Sweller, 1988); phonological flexibility (Dehaene, 2018)
Linguistic mixing and code interference	Pupils	"I speak Mozabite at home, classical Arabic at school, and now French and English. I mix everything up."	Working memory limits (Sweller et al., 2019); translanguaging (García & Wei, 2014)
Mechanical memorisation without comprehension	Teachers	"The children repeat English words without understanding them, just to satisfy the instruction."	Cognitive load theory (Sweller, 1988); demotivation (Dörnyei, 2001)

Inter-language sound interference	Teacher s	"Pupils hesitate between 'au', 'ai', and 'a', especially when they have just been working in English."	Neuroplasticity and sound assimilation (Dehaene, 2018; Syka & Merzenich, 2005)
Loss of linguistic identity insecurity	Parents /	"My daughter says she is good at no language. She feels lost between Arabic, French, and English."	Linguistic identity construction (Catroux & Jamin, 2019); identity weakening (Wittorski, 2016)
Linguistic anxiety and oral avoidance	Parents	"My child hesitates to speak. He is afraid of getting things wrong and sometimes prefers to say nothing."	Foreign language anxiety (Horwitz et al., 1986); anxiety-demotivation cycle (MacIntyre & Gardner, 1991)
Cognitive fatigue overload	Parents /	"My son says he has to learn too many things at once and can't keep up."	Cognitive overload (Sweller, 1988); working memory limits (Sweller et al., 2019)
Mother-tongue instability	Parents	"My son mixes languages when he talks. At home he uses our mother tongue, but he inserts French or English words he doesn't always understand."	Mother-tongue consolidation (Vincent, 2024); linguistic confusion (Benadidou, 2019)

Table 1 reveals three analytically distinct layers of difficulty. At the cognitive level, participants across all groups report phonological confusion, code interference, and cognitive fatigue, findings consistent with Sweller's (1988) cognitive load theory and with the working memory constraints identified in Section 3. At the affective level, pupils and parents describe linguistic anxiety, loss of confidence, and oral avoidance, consistent with the anxiety-demotivation cycle documented by Horwitz et al. (1986) and MacIntyre and Gardner (1991). At the identity level, testimonies, particularly from parents, reflect a weakening of the mother-tongue foundation and a sense of linguistic insecurity, which aligns with the identity construction framework discussed in Section 9. It is important to note that these findings represent participants' perceptions and reported experiences under specific implementation conditions; they do not constitute evidence that multilingualism itself is harmful. The theoretical literature reviewed in Sections 3.1–3.3 suggests that these difficulties are best explained by inadequate scaffolding and the absence of prior mother-tongue consolidation rather than by exposure to multiple languages per se. Several questions remain open for future research: whether the observed difficulties diminish over time with improved pedagogy; whether individual variables such as socio-economic background and regional mother tongue moderate the effects; and whether a phased introduction model would produce different outcomes.

12. Pedagogical Recommendations

Use of technology: Integrating interactive digital tools (applications, online platforms) that make learning more engaging and less burdensome.

Psychological support: Setting up listening and dialogue spaces to help pupils cope with stress and fatigue.

Parent involvement: Raising families' awareness of the importance of balancing learning and rest, and involving them in monitoring their children's progress.

Cultural activities: Supplementing teaching with artistic and cultural activities (films, songs, exchanges) that stimulate motivation without adding to academic pressure.

These recommendations aim to reduce cognitive and emotional overload while maintaining the quality of language teaching. They rest on better organisation, adapted pedagogy, and active collaboration between teachers, pupils, and parents.

13. Conclusion

The theoretical and empirical findings of this study suggest that the simultaneous teaching of French and English alongside Arabic in Algerian primary schools remains problematic under current conditions, characterised by insufficient pedagogical support, limited resources, and the lack of prior mother-tongue consolidation. Evidence from the literature and participants' testimonies points to cognitive overload, linguistic confusion, and reduced motivation. However, this study does not argue against multilingualism itself. Research on translanguaging, additive multilingualism, and mother-tongue-based multilingual education demonstrates that multilingual learning can be beneficial when it is age-appropriate, adequately supported, and built on a stable linguistic foundation. The issue identified here concerns implementation rather than principle.

These findings call for a reconsideration of language education policies in Algeria. Rather than multiplying early language learning demands, priority should be given to a progressive approach that respects pupils' cognitive and developmental needs. Such a strategy would help transform language learning into a source of achievement and personal growth rather than overload and discouragement.

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